

PERSONALITY TRAITS AS THE POTENTIAL PREDICTORS OF DOPING ATTITUDES AMONG ELITE VARSITY STUDENT ATHLETES

Komal Wazir¹, Fariq Ahmed², Dr. Muhammad Azam³, Qaisar Ali⁴, Dr. Asif Ali⁵

¹BS Physical Education & Sports Sciences, Government College University Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan.

²M.Phil. scholar, Department of Physical Education & Sports Sciences, Government College University Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan.

³Assistant Professor, Department of Physical Education & Sports Sciences, Government College University Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan.

⁴BS Physical Education & Sports Sciences, Government College University Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan.

⁵Associate Professor, Department of Physical Education & Sports Sciences, Government College University Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan.

¹komalwazir266@gmail.com, ²fariq.ahmed@gcu.edu.pk, ³m.azam@gcu.edu.pk, ⁴qaisarmanj49@gmail.com,

⁵asif.ali@gcu.edu.pk

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Corresponding Author: *

Dr. Asif Ali

Abstract

Objective: The present study aimed to investigate whether personality traits function as potential predictors of doping attitudes among elite varsity student athletes.

Background: Elite athletes, particularly those pursuing an academic degree at a higher education institution, are surrounded with highly demanding and competitive environment. This is because their academic workload is eventually merged with their intense athletic commitments. The urge to win in front of their fellow peers at any cost and the escalating competitiveness of the evolving sports might drive some desperate elite varsity student athletes to utilize any available means to gain a competitive advantage. However, personality traits among the psychological predictors might work as important and crucial determinants of the doping behaviors and attitudes.

Methodology: A total of 320 participants of which 163 were female varsity elite student athletes and 157 were male elite varsity student athletes were made part of this study. Their ages spanned from 18 to 25 in years and were participating in multiple sports at elite levels (International and National). Participants filled out the Big Five Inventory-10 (BFI-10) and the Performance Enhancement Attitude Scale-17 (PEAS-17), alongside with a demographic scale.

Results: Model 1 of the regression analysis indicated that sports experience was moderately negatively associated to doping attitudes among elite varsity student athletes. This suggested that higher sports experience may promote lower doping attitudes in this particular group. Secondly, model 2 revealed that along with sports experience, personality traits also significantly negatively predicted doping attitudes among varsity elite student athletes. Whereas, among the personality traits only extraversion and openness traits were significantly negatively linked to doping attitudes within this population group.

Conclusion: The findings offer new insights into how extraversion and openness relate to doping attitudes among elite university athletes while emphasizing the need of psychological profiling in anti-doping education and programs.

INTRODUCTION

Elite athletes, particularly those pursuing an academic degree at a higher education institution, are surrounded with highly demanding and competitive environment (Mateu et al., 2025). This is because their academic workload is eventually merged with their intense athletic commitments while making it highly challenging for them (Rose & Burton, 2024). They are further exposed to immense pressures while competing due to the presence of their fellow university peers at most events (Ridwan et al., 2023). The urge to win in front of their fellow peers at any cost and the escalating competitiveness of the evolving sports might drive some desperate elite varsity student athletes to utilize any available means to gain a competitive advantage (Praet et al., 2025). Due to which, positive attitudes towards doping have become increasingly alarming among elite varsity student athletes (Haugen & Solberg, 2024). Recent evidence extracted from latest research has indicated that positive doping attitudes are gradually rising among varsity student athlete population belonging to diverse sports groups. For instance, a study conducted on varsity student athletes of sports sciences discipline in Germany reported around 11.2 % of positive doping attitudes and drug use among them (Thevis et al., 2008). Similarly, a pilot study conducted in the Egypt found that among the student athlete population, 13.8% of the male and less than 10% of the female student athletes reported to use the high performance enhancing substance (Badr el Dine & Attia, 2022). These high attitudes towards doping may have serious consequences on both physical and psychological health of student athletes (Adami et al., 2022). Physical consequences may include cardiovascular related diseases and liver damage whereas, psychological disturbances may involve increased anxiety and depression levels (Berger et al., 2024). Given this substantially high and favorable attitude towards the utilization of doping techniques among young elite varsity student athletes, it has become highly

essential to devise its mitigating mechanisms. If focusing on the psychological dimension, personality traits might fall among the few probable mechanisms that may serve as potential protective factors against positive doping attitudes. Personality traits, on the other hand, can be summarized as the persistent psychological characteristics that influence an individual's behavior, feelings and thoughts across a variety of contexts (Angelini, 2023). While keeping the athletic domain in focus, each trait of personality plays a fundamental role in regulating stress, shaping motivation and ethical choices (Louwen et al., 2023). For instance, the trait conscientiousness has been reported to support discipline during training while agreeableness trait might promote team-work and cooperation among athletes (Levin, 2024; Pindar et al., 2022). In a similar realm, the traits extraversion and openness have been associated with healthy and resilient coping practices, active and positive social behavior and improved moral awareness with in athlete population (Allen et al., 2021; Piepiora, 2024). However, these personality traits may notably influence the attitude of elite varsity student athletes who compete under extreme pressure and may opt for doping as a coping mechanism (Yang et al., 2024). Whereas, to design preventive strategies, it is extremely essential to first understand the potential pathways of behavior through which the personality of an individual might shape doping attitudes.

Contrary to the growing global attention to doping in the competitive sport, there still exists limited number of research on how personality traits might influence doping attitudes among elite varsity student athletes. In particular, this gap is especially notable among elite varsity athlete population because past studies conducted in this regard have chosen either recreational athletes or professional adults as their study sample (Grasdalsmoen et al., 2022). Elite varsity student athletes are at the critical and formative stages of

their lives (Sato et al., 2023). During this stage, they may develop a unique identity, plan a long-term career approach and might also develop moral reasoning (Kegelaers et al., 2024). All these factors might eventually interact with personality traits to shape positive or negative doping attitudes among varsity elite athletes (Nikander et al., 2022). At present, no research study has examined or assessed personality traits as the potential predictors of doping attitudes among elite varsity student athletes thus forming a clear research gap.

Objective of the study

Therefore, the present study aims to investigate whether personality traits function as potential predictors of doping attitudes among elite varsity student athletes. By examining the associations between key personality dimensions and doping attitudes, this research seeks to provide valuable insights for coaches, sports psychologists, and university athletic departments. The findings may support the development of targeted anti-doping education programs, personality-informed counseling strategies, and preventive interventions that promote ethical decision-making and safeguard athlete well-being. Ultimately, this study aims to contribute to a stronger, more psychologically informed understanding of doping vulnerability within university sports settings.

Materials and Methods

Design of the study

With respect to the design of this study, it was conducted by adapting a descriptive cross-sectional approach.

Population and Sample

Purposive sampling technique was utilized to gather data from both female and male participants. To be precise, elite varsity student athletes from ten public and private sector universities of a major city of Pakistan were considered as the initial population for the study. G power software was employed to outline the final sample of the study. While considering five independent variables and one dependent variable with medium effect size and a significance level of 0.05, G Power software estimated around 92

participants as the minimum required sample size. We however collected data from a total of 320 participants of which 163 were female elite student athletes and 157 were male elite varsity student athletes. Their ages spanned from 18 to 25 in years and were participating in multiple sports at elite levels (International and National).

Data Collection tool

Following are the three sections of the tool that was employed to gather data for this study.

Section 1: Demographics

A basic, self-administrated demographic survey was adopted to gather the information about the participants. The structure of the demographic questionnaire was as follows; gender, athletic level, sports name, sports experience in years, marital status, age, study program, academic year, department name and university.

Section 2: Big Five Inventory – 10 (BFI-10)

The second section of the data collection tool comprised of a ten-item questionnaire that was focused on assessing the personality traits of the participants. This tool, also known as BFI-10 was developed by Rammstedt et al. (2013). The reliability and validity of this tool can be observed from earlier studies that reported its Cronbach Alpha's value spanning between 0.713 – 0.924 (Ndofirepi & Steyn, 2023; Rammstedt et al., 2023). Lastly, before initiating the process of data gathering, the permission from the developer of the tool was obtained.

Section 3: The Performance Enhancement Attitude Scale – 17 (PEAS-17)

A 17-item questionnaire was used to assess an athlete's attitude and beliefs in regards to the use of drugs or substances that enhances the performance during sports. This tool also known as PEAS-17 utilizes a six-point Likert Scale and was developed by Petróczi and Aidman (2009). The Cronbach Alpha's score of this tool in previous studies was reported to be ranged between 0.71 to 0.91 which demonstrates its good reliability and validity (Chebet, 2014; Deng et al., 2022). However, in this study, PEAS exhibited a Cronbach alpha score of 0.72. Similar to the

previous tool, permission from the developer of this tool was also acquired prior to its usage.

Procedure

The procedure for the data collection involved a direct and in-person interaction with the participants of the study. Before starting the data collection process, the authors first acquired informed consent of the participants and explained how to respond to the items of the questionnaire. The participants were also provided with a quick introduction to the research topic before asking them to fill the questionnaire. Additionally, all the contributors were aware that their contribution in this research was completely optional and they can draw out from the study at any phase in time if they are not willing to complete the questionnaire. They were also informed that all the data collected will be kept completely confidential.

Data Analysis

Data analysis was conducted using SPSS v.27 (2019) to determine the relationship between BFPTs and doping attitude. The following statistical procedures were applied: 1) Firstly, we tested all the necessary assumptions likewise linearity, normality, multicollinearity,

homoscedasticity, and independence error all were met; 2) Secondly, descriptive statistics was initially applied to summarize the demographic and psychometric data; 3) Lastly, hierarchical multiple regression HMR analysis was applied to assess the predictive power of the personality traits on doping attitudes while controlling for demographic variables. The value of significance was set at < 0.05 .

Results

Participant Characteristics

The study included 320 participants that were almost distributed fairly by gender with 49.1% as male ($n = 157$) and 50.9% as female ($n = 163$). Most participants (88.4%, $n = 283$) competed at the national level, while a smaller group (11.6%, $n = 37$) competed internationally. Regarding academic year, 12.5% ($n = 40$) were first-year students, 31.6% ($n = 101$) were in their second year, 28.7% ($n = 92$) in their third year, and 27.2% ($n = 87$) in their fourth year. The average age was 21.05 years ($SD = 1.641$), and participants reported about 5.4 years ($SD = 2.416$) of sports experience. (See Table 1)

Table 1: Characteristics of Elite Varsity Student Athletes

Variables	Category	N	%	M	SD
Gender	Male	157	49.1		
	Female	163	50.9		
Playing level	National	283	88.4		
	International	37	11.6		
Academic year	First year	40	12.5		
	Second year	101	31.6		
	Third year	92	28.7		
	Fourth year	87	27.2		
Age				21.05	1.641
Sports experience				5.40	2.416

Hierarchical Multiple Regression Analysis

The ANOVA results of the hierarchical regression of university elite athletes were summarized in Table 2. During correlational analysis, only sport experience from the demographic factors demonstrated substantial correlation with doping behaviors. Therefore, in step 1 of the analysis, we added sports experience as the independent

variable. The results of model 1 were significant with $F = 7.124$ and $p = .008$. This showed that sports experience greatly explained the variation in doping attitude. In model 2, personality traits were added along with sports experiences. This inclusion of personality traits made the model even better with $F = 4.280$ and $p = .000$.

Table 2: The ANOVA summary of hierarchical regression for elite athletes

Model		Sum of square	df	Mean square	f	P
1	Regression	927.484	1	927.484	7.124	.008 ^b
	Residual	41401.988	318	130.195		
	Total	42329.472	319			
2	Regression	3209.508	6	534.918	4.280	.000 ^c
	Residual	39119.964	313	124.984		
	Total	42329.472	319			

The direction of the relationship between sports experience and doping attitudes as a result of hierarchical regression analysis was negative ($B = -0.706$, $p = .008$). This indicated that elite varsity student athletes with increased or higher sports experiences tended to possess lower doping attitudes.

After the addition of personality traits in model 2 along with sports experience, the overall model stayed negatively significant with doping attitudes. However, only the traits extraversion ($B = -2.093$, $SE = 0.761$, $\beta = -0.153$, $t = -2.749$, $p =$

0.006) and openness ($B = -2.404$, $SE = 0.913$, $\beta = -0.146$, $t = -2.633$, $p = 0.009$) were negatively significant with doping attitudes. This suggested that varsity elite student athletes with higher scores in extraversion and openness tended to possess lower level of doping attitudes. Whereas, the remaining traits of personality: agreeableness ($p = .248$), neuroticism ($p = .772$) and conscientiousness ($p = .621$) were not statistically significant with doping attitudes. (See Table 3)

Table 3: Summary of hierarchical regression analysis for elite athletes

Model	variables	B	SE	β	t	P
1	Sports experiences	-.706	.264	-.148	-2.669	.008
2	Sports experiences	-.568	.261	-.119	-2.172	.031
	Extraversion	-2.093	.761	-.153	-2.749	.006
	Agreeableness	-.990	.855	-.064	-1.157	.248
	Conscientiousness	.409	.827	.027	.495	.621
	Neuroticism	.237	.816	.016	.290	.772
	Openness	-2.404	.913	-.146	-2.633	.009

Discussion

In the recent few years, elite varsity student athletes have actively been investigated by researchers due to their constant exposure to multiple athletic, academic and peer pressures. However, there is limited to no research on the relationship between doping attitudes and personality traits within this specific student athlete group. Therefore, to explore whether personality traits function as potential predictors of doping attitudes among elite varsity student athletes or not was the main aim of this research. Model 1 of the regression analysis indicated that sports experience was moderately negatively associated to doping attitudes among elite varsity student athletes. This suggested that higher sports experience may promote lower doping attitudes in this particular group. Secondly, model 2 revealed that along with sports experience, personality traits also significantly negatively predicted doping attitudes among varsity elite student athletes. Whereas, among the personality traits only extraversion and openness traits were significantly negatively linked to doping attitudes within this population group. These results proposed that varsity elite student athletes with higher levels of openness and extraversion traits might possess lower doping attitudes.

The initial model of the regression analysis revealed that varsity elite student athletes with higher sports experience may tend to exhibit lower positive doping attitudes. These findings are consistent with a couple of studies conducted in this regard on varying populations. For instance, a study conducted in Malaysia on student athlete population with a similar objective presented parallel results. The findings revealed that student athletes with increased experience levels in sports were less prone to doping attitudes and use (Chiang et al., 2018). Correspondingly, another study conducted on a higher scale in UK, USA and Canada also presented resembling outcomes. The study involved student athletes as its target population and proposed that increased sports experience might influence positively on negative doping attitudes (Erickson et al., 2019). Due to continuous participation in competitive or elite environments, varsity elite student athletes may

develop a sense of responsibility and increased respect for sports integrity. They may further be exposed to various national and international anti-doping seminars and workshops which may to some extent may have discouraged doping attitudes.

This study also revealed that high scores of Extraversion trait were significantly negatively associated to doping attitudes among elite varsity student athletes. This appeared to suggest that those elite varsity student athletes who demonstrate high extraversion levels might corresponded to less favorable attitudes toward doping. As no antecedent investigation has previously selected varsity elite student athletes as its sample population therefore, no similar studies were found. However, several past studies conducted with a similar objective on other population types did present similar results. For example, Berger et al. (2024) found that the trait extraversion was negatively whereas the trait neuroticism was positively associated with doping among adolescents. Similarly, Li et al. (2024) also proposed that the association between doping attitudes and personality traits was negative in nature among athletes participating in individual sports. Although to devise or outline the possible mechanisms behind this association was not the objective of the study. However, it can be endorsed that due to high extraversion levels varsity elite student athletes may be more socially engaged and influenced by their peers. Due to this reason, there is a high susceptibility for them to stick to ethical standards and team values rather than relying upon doping.

Similar to extraversion trait, the study also presented similar outcomes for Openness trait. The results highlighted that openness personality trait was negatively in connection with doping attitudes among varsity elite student athletes. This suggested that those student athletes who exhibited high openness levels were less prone to doping attitudes. As this was the first ever study to examine the interplay between doping attitudes and personality traits among varsity elite student athlete population. Therefore, it was difficult to discuss these findings with similar studies. However, a couple of studies have been conducted

in a similar context on other population groups that presented similar outcomes. For example, a research study conducted by Ring et al. (2022) on collegiate athletes proposed that heightened openness levels were negatively linked to doping attitudes. In a similar realm, another study on collegiate athletes conducted in China's southeastern province presented equivalent results. This study by Ni and Feng (2023) revealed that high openness traits were linked to low positive doping attitudes. Athletes that have high score in openness trait, which is also known for curiosity, exploring new experiences, and mental flexibility may either think carefully about using doping due to ethical issues. Hence, understanding the contributions of extraversion and openness might turn out to be fruitful in explaining the psychological reasons behind doping attitude or behavior in sports of elite level.

Practical implication:

The results of this study might offer several important and meaningful practical implications to promote clean-sport behaviors. Primarily, the findings encourage the universities and sports organizations to implement mentorship programs that are headed by experienced or senior players of similar institution. This will assist young and upcoming varsity elite student athletes in understanding sports ethics and take hands on experience from their fellow senior athletes. Secondly, by offering additional support and tailoring psychological interventions to those varsity elite student athletes who possess low extraversion or openness levels, anti-doping education might be enhanced.

Future Research:

Future studies should include larger and more diverse groups from different sports and schools to confirm these results. Additionally, long-term studies that track changes over time could provide more insights into the relationship between doping attitudes and personality traits. Conversely, anti-doping programs might be more effective if they consider individual personality traits, allowing for more personalized approaches to help athletes resist doping.

Conclusion:

To examine whether personality traits function as potential predictors of doping attitudes among elite varsity student athletes was the primary objective of this study. The results proposed that athletes who exhibited higher levels of extraversion trait and were highly open to new experiences tended to be less supportive of performance enhancing drugs. These traits might be helpful in protecting athletes by encouraging better ethical choices in high pressure sports settings.

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